

Dissociation Constants and Thermodynamic Functions of Substituted-quinolines

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Dissociation constants of hydroxyquinoline derivatives have been determined at 20, 30 and 40° in pyridine-water mixed solvent system at two different ionic strength of electrolyte KCl. The thermodynamic functions, viz. ΔG , ΔH and ΔS have been calculated and discussed on the basis of inductive and resonance effects.

THE dissociation constants of 4-hydroxy-quinoline-carboxylic ester (4-HQC), 6-nitro-4-hydroxy-quinoline-3-carboxylic ester (6-NHQC), 7-nitro-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic ester (7-NHQC), 8-nitro-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic ester (8-NHQC), 8-hydroxyquinoline (8-HQ) in pyridine-water mixed solvent system of varying compositions, different ionic strengths and at three temperatures were studied earlier¹. The results thus obtained have been utilised in ascertaining the dependence of these dissociation constants on the temperature variations and their thermodynamic functions.

Dissociation constant determinations have been carried out at three different temperatures and the values reported for various compounds are useful for comparative study. The variation of dissociation constant with change in temperature concur with the theoretical expectations. As temperature increases degree of dissociation increases, resulting an increase in dissociation constant (K_a) values.

Positive values of free energy changes (ΔG) indicate non-spontaneous character of dissociation reaction (Table 1). Increase in dielectric constant of the media favours spontaneity of the reaction

TABLE 1 - ΔG OF VARIOUS COMPOUNDS AT TWO DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTHS AND AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURE

Solvent = Pyridine-water (50 : 50, v/v), dielectric constant = 45.5

Compd.	ΔG at $\mu = 0.0101 M$			ΔG at $\mu = 0.0014 M$		
	20°	30°	40°	20°	30°	40°
8-HQ	15.10	15.35	15.66	15.16	15.56	15.84
4-HQC	14.27	14.38	14.62	14.63	14.81	15.84
6-NHQC	15.28	15.25	15.38	15.58	15.60	15.74
7-NHQC	13.26	13.56	13.89	13.34	13.64	13.93
8-NHQC	12.47	12.69	12.10	12.62	12.80	13.05

(Table 2). The increasing temperature too has similar effect on ΔG (Table 3).

TABLE 2 - ΔG VALUES OF 8-HYDROXYQUINOLINE

Temp. = 30°, $\mu = 0.0101 M$

Solvent Pyridine-water (v/v)	Dielectric constant	ΔG
50 : 50	32.0	16.25
60 : 40	38.5	15.70
70 : 30	45.5	15.10
Water	78.4	12.23

TABLE 3 - ΔG VALUES OF 8-HYDROXYQUINOLINE

$\mu = 0.0101 M$

Solvent	ΔG		
	20°	30°	40°
Pyridine-water 50 : 50 (v/v)	15.10	15.35	15.66

Increase in K_a values with temperature indicates endothermic reaction and positive values for enthalpy changes (ΔH) (Table 4). The solvation effect^{2,3} of the solvent media decrease the total number of ions of the dissociated quinolines resulting in the negative entropy (ΔS) (Table 5).

TABLE 4 - CHANGE IN ENTHALPY (ΔH , kcal mol⁻¹) OF VARIOUS COMPOUNDS

Compd.	Temp. difference 11° between 20° and 30°		Temp. difference 10° between 30° and 40°	
	$\mu = 0.0101 M$	$\mu = 0.0014 M$	$\mu = 0.0101 M$	$\mu = 0.0014 M$
8-HQ	7.12	3.66	6.08	6.94
4-HQC	10.97	9.34	6.94	13.84
6-NHQC	16.25	15.03	11.24	11.24
7-NHQC	4.47	2.97	8.24	4.30
8-NHQC	6.09	7.31	3.47	5.21

TABLE 5 - CHANGE IN ENTROPY (ΔS , cal mol⁻¹) FOR VARIOUS COMPOUNDS

Solvent = Pyridine - water (50 : 50, v/v), dielectric constant = 45.5

Compd.	At $\mu = 0.01 M$			At $\mu = 0.0014 M$		
	20°	30°	40°	20°	30°	40°
8-HQ	-25.19	-25.19	-30.60	-39.27	-39.27	-28.44
4-HQC	-11.25	-11.25	-24.53	-18.03	-18.03	-3.18
6-NHQC	3.30	3.30	-13.23	-1.86	-1.87	-14.38
7-NHQC	-30.00	-30.00	-18.06	-35.10	-25.23	-30.84

Nitro-group substitution in the 4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic ester has a strong electron-withdrawing ability leading to inductive^{4,5} and resonance effect⁶. This decreases the electron density around oxygen atom enabling easy release of H, and resulting in increased K_a values.

The structures 2, 3 and 4 clearly indicate the inductive effect of nitro group on the parent compound 4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic ester anion (1). In the 7-nitro derivative (3), the shift in electron density cannot be represented, suggesting that the inductive effect is not transmitted to the functional group OH in the parent nucleus. This shows that nitro group substituted at the 7th position should exhibit the least inductive effect giving lower dissociation constant. Out of the 6-nitro and 8-nitro derivatives, the 6th position is found to be the nearest to the functional group OH, which implies that the effect should be the greatest at this position. Thus, the theoretical order of pK_a values due to inductive effect comes out be 6-nitro > 8-nitro > 7-nitro.

Resonance effect: As shown earlier, in the equilibrium,

the strength of the acid Y-H depends upon its ability to donate proton. Conversely, the strength depends upon the reluctance of its conjugate base to accept the proton. In other words, the increased stability of the conjugate base tends to increase the acid strength Y-H being more stabilised compared with Y-H, recombination of proton with Y⁻ is discouraged and the equilibrium is shifted to the right.

In the present study, where hydroxyquinolines were made use of, the anions were found to be more stabilised than the neutral molecules.

Structures 5 and 6 are the resonance hybrids of the neutral molecule and 7 and 8 being that of the anion (intermediate structures not shown). Due to the greater charge separation in 6, which is the resonance hybrid of the neutral molecule, it is less stabilised than 8 which is the resonance hybrid of the anion (5). In cases where nitro (NO₂) group which is a highly electron-withdrawing group attached (6-nitro-, 7-nitro- and 8-nitro-4-hydroxyquinoline-3-carboxylic esters), a greater delocalisation of the negative charge causes further increase in acidity of the molecules, except in the 7-nitro derivative (9 and 10 for 8-nitro derivative; 11 and 12 for 6-nitro derivative).

The electron-withdrawing effect will be absent in the 7th position.

TABLE 6 - EFFECT OF SUBSTITUTION ON DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS

Temp. = 20°, $\mu = 0.0101 M$

Solvent Pyridine - water (v/v)	pK_a				
	8-HQ	4-HQC	6-NHQC	7-NHQC	8-NHQC
50 : 50	11.26	10.64	11.40	9.89	9.30
60 : 60	11.71	10.83	11.93	9.94	9.34
70 : 70	12.12	11.07	12.69	9.94	9.39
Water	9.15	9.75	8.35	9.50	9.10

The results (Table 6) reveal that the acidity increases in the order, 8-nitro > 7-nitro > 6-nitro, in pyridine-water mixtures, whereas it follows the order, 6 nitro > 8-nitro > 7-nitro in pure aqueous media, which is in accordance with that of the predicted values.

References

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